
Analysis of the use of Gender-Based Violence Complaint Information System Application

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ABSTRACT: In order to prevent the spread of gender-based violence, it is a shared burden and responsibility to understand the root causes of various case records. The causes of gender-based violence are quite diverse. Based on this, the urgency of this research is to develop a web-based gender-based violence reporting application for women and children that becomes a responsive complaint media and reaches people located in remote areas of Bengkalis Regency. The purpose of this study is to make it easier for the public to report acts of violence independently through web-based applications in accordance with the 2P program so that cases of violence can be handled quickly and responsively by related parties, especially LK3 of the Bengkalis Regency Social Service and UP2A. Meanwhile, the specific purpose of the study is to design a web-based application that can report acts of gender-based violence by attaching evidence in the form of photos of victims and supporting documents in the reporting. On this website, the reporter can fill in a biodata that has been listed on the complaint form, this convenience is not only for the complainant but also makes it easier for the admin to recap the report. The result of this research is the creation of an application for a complaint information system for gender-based violence cases with the name of the *PKBG.org* website which functions for the people of Bengkalis Regency to be able to easily report acts of violence that occur against themselves and the surrounding environment quickly, through the *PKBG.org* website. This makes it easier for admins to make reports of gender-based violence that occur in Bengkalis Regency, Violence reporting data is stored well in the database so that it makes it easier for the government to take action in decision-making for the government to reach and handle cases.

KEYWORDS: Information Systems, Violence Complaints, Gender Bias

I. INTRODUCTION

Information System (SI) is a system that combines the role of humans with the use of technology to support the information management process in an organization. This system functions in the activities of collecting, storing, processing, and distributing the information needed. Its supporting components include hardware, software, human resources, databases, and procedures that are integrated and work in an integrated manner [1].

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is a form of violence experienced by a person due to their gender or gender identity. This action is carried out by means of coercion, violence, threats, manipulation, socio-cultural pressure, and economic factors so that the victim is forced to do things against his will. Although the majority of victims are women and girls, LGBTIQ+ groups, boys, and men are also potential victims of GBV [2].

According to Komnas Perempuan, violence is divided into two main categories, namely violence in the public sphere and violence in the personal sphere. Violence in the public sphere includes obscenity, sexual harassment, and rape. Meanwhile, violence in the personal realm includes violence against wives (KTI), violence in dating relationships, violence against children, and violence against domestic workers [3].

The issue of gender equality is currently increasingly being voiced by various parties with diverse backgrounds, ranging from government institutions to activists and gender activists. Gender justice campaign efforts are carried out through online media and direct activities in public spaces. Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is understood as a form of violence that is directly directed at individuals based on their gender or gender. These behaviors can be in the form of physical, sexual, psychological violence, coercion, threats, and actions that limit individual freedom related to gender. These various forms of violence can develop into certain crimes, such as sexual violence that leads to sexual harassment or exploitation. In addition, psychological violence can trigger other crimes such as the spread of hoaxes and defamation motivated by gender bias [4].

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Cases of gender-based violence in Indonesia showed an increase in 2021 compared to the previous year. Based on the Komnas Perempuan Annual Report, which is a national routine report on cases of gender-based violence against women, there was a surge of almost 50% in 2022. There were 338,496 complaints about KBG cases in 2021, which were collected through the Religious Justice Agency, service institutions, and Komnas Perempuan [4].

The Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection reported that from January 1 to May 19, 2021, there were 4,696 cases of violence against women and children. Of this total, 2,742 cases occurred in households. In addition, 611 cases were recorded in public facilities, 100 cases in schools, 62 cases in the workplace, and five other cases in non-formal educational institutions [5].

In Riau Province, cases of physical violence against women are still relatively high. Based on the results of a survey by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), as many as 4.27% of women experience physical violence committed by their husbands or partners. The main causative factors include power inequality in relationships (56.25%), family problems (43.75%), economic problems (37.5%), and other factors (43.75%). In addition, 1.87% of physical violence against women was committed by family members, 1.07% by co-workers, and 0.27% by superiors and other perpetrators with a similar percentage [6].

The cases of violence that occurred in Bengkalis Regency, Riau Province, based on data from the Bengkalis Regency Police, UP2A, and LK3, are presented in the following table:

Yes	Case Type	Quantity	Percentage
1	Child Custody Cases	18	5.79
2	Missing Child Case	1	0.32
3	Bullying Case	2	0.64
4	The Case of Curanmor	1	0.32
5	School Rights Case	2	0.64
6	Child Violence Cases	34	10.93
7	Child Delinquency Cases	4	1.29
8	Lakalantas Case	18	5.79
9	Drug Cases	2	0.64
10	Beating Case	3	0.96
11	Cases of Abuse	66	21.22
12	Theft Cases	12	3.86
13	Theft by Violence	1	0.32
14	Cases of Neglect	5	1.61
15	Persecution Cases	13	4.18
16	Demolition Cases	5	1.61
17	A Case of Sexual Assault	114	36.66
18	Trapeking Case	3	0.96
19	Sexual Harassment	7	2.25
TOTAL		311	100

Source: Police, Up2A, LK3 Bengkalis Regency

Although there are currently facilities available to report cases of violence, the number of violent incidents in Bengkalis Regency is still relatively high. This is because the complaint mechanism that is still running is still conventional. Victims of violence are required to come directly to the Family Counseling Service (LK3) office of the Social Service or to the relevant UP2A to report the violent events they experienced.

One of the main factors that affect the high number of cases of violence in Bengkalis Regency is the limited public access to the location of the LK3 of the Bengkalis Regency Social Service and P2TP2A of Bengkalis Regency, as well as the lack of public understanding of the procedure for reporting violence. The current reporting process requires the complainant to visit or contact the LK3 expert staff of the Social Service. Furthermore, the incoming report will be forwarded to the complaint officer for verification, both related to elements of gender-based violence and the possibility of political content. After the verification process, the report will be forwarded to the monitoring department for follow-up. However, the complaint system that is still running has not been supported by the implementation of an adequate information system so that it has not been able to provide convenience for victims in submitting reports.

Based on the high number of cases of gender-based violence in Bengkalis Regency, the author designed a web-based application that aims to make it easier for people to report violent incidents experienced online. This Gender-Based Violence Complaint Information System allows reporters to fill in their personal data through the complaint form that has been provided. This convenience is not only felt by the reporter, but also helps the administrator in recording and recapitulating reports more efficiently [7].

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Improving the quality of public services is part of bureaucratic reform efforts in providing services to the community. So far, the quality of public services is still considered suboptimal, as shown by the high number of public complaints related to services submitted directly to public service units and government apparatus.

In an effort to reduce the number of violence, the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection launched the 2P Program (Complainant and Pioneer). This program aims to encourage active community participation in reporting and preventing acts of violence against victims and potential victims in the surrounding environment. The Pioneer plays the role of an agent of change who dares to act and invites the community to fight violence, while the Whistleblower is an individual who actively conveys information when there is a violation of rights against himself or others around him or her [8].

To support the success of the 2P Program, the availability of facilities and infrastructure that are able to facilitate the reporting of acts of violence in real time and can be widely accessed by the community. The use of information technology, especially information systems, has been widely applied in various sectors, including in the administration of government [8].

Based on this description, the urgency of this research is to develop a web-based application for reporting gender-based violence against women and children as a responsive complaint media and able to reach the community to remote areas of Bengkalis Regency. The general purpose of this research is to make it easier for the public to report acts of violence independently through a web-based application that is in line with the 2P Program, so that cases of violence can be handled quickly and appropriately by related parties, especially LK3 of the Bengkalis Regency Social Service and UP2A. The specific purpose of this research is to design a web-based application that allows gender-based violence reporting by attaching supporting evidence in the form of photos of victims and related documents.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

One of the commonly used approaches in system design and development is the Waterfall method, also known as the Waterfall method. *Linear Sequential Model* or *Classic Life Cycle*. This model was first introduced around 1970 and although it is classified as a classic method, it is still widely applied today in the field of software engineering (*Software Engineering*). The Waterfall model describes the process of developing a system that is carried out in stages and sequentially. In general, the stages of system development with the Waterfall method include the following phases [7]:

1) Planning

The planning stage involves users related to the processing of value data to identify system needs and set goals to be achieved through the design of the information system. The information obtained at this stage becomes the basis for the next analysis process.

2) Analysis

At the analysis stage, an assessment of the current system is carried out. This process typically uses *flowmaps* to get a comprehensive overview of the workflow and mechanisms of the existing system.

3) Design

The design stage focuses on designing the system to be developed. This design refers to the *proposed flowmap* and context diagram as a guideline in building system structures and components.

4) Implementation

The implementation stage is the process of translating the system design into an application. At this stage, programming activities (*coding*) and testing of the design results are carried out so that the system can function properly and make it easier for users to operate.

5) Conclusion

The final step is to draw conclusions from the entire system design process, with an emphasis on the level of user satisfaction with the system that has been developed.

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A Picture of the Waterfall Model System Development Pass

The model follows a systematic and stage-oriented approach, which starts with the general planning of system development, then proceeds to the analysis of system requirements, as well as gradually through the phases of system design, programming, system testing, and maintenance [7].

1. System Planning

At the design stage, an object-oriented approach is applied by using *UML (Unified Modeling Language)* as a modeling tool. The goal of this stage is to establish a clear foundation for the subsequent implementation of the system, so that the functional structure, objectives, and logical flow of the system can be defined unequivocally [9].

2. Programming

The web-based system developed in this study uses *PHP* as the main programming language and *MySQL* as the database management system for data storage and management.

3. System Analysis

System analysis is carried out using the *PARTS*, which serves as the main instrument for identifying fundamental system problems. In this analysis, various dimensions are considered, including system performance, information quality, economic aspects, security control, efficiency, and service quality. This approach is known as analysis *PARTS (Performance, Information, Economy, Control, Efficiency, and Service)*. Execution of analysis *PARTS* Before the development of information systems is very important because it allows the identification of the main problems and the factors that affect them. In this study, six dimensions of assessment were used [7]:

- 1) Performance refers to the ability of the system to complete tasks in a short time and achieve preset goals. Performance appraisals are generally based on *throughput* levels and *response time*. *Throughput* indicates the number of tasks that the system can process in a given period of time.
- 2) Information Information Quality is a key factor in the success of system operations. Quality information allows management and users to make informed decisions. A good information system produces accurate, timely, and relevant information. This dimension assesses the system's ability to generate useful information.
- 3) Economy Economic analysis focuses on the comparison between the costs incurred in the implementation of the system and the benefits generated. An effective information system is expected to be able to reduce operational costs while providing economic added value for the organization.
- 4) Control The control aspect is mainly related to system security, including data backup mechanisms and protection against unauthorized access. This analysis includes supervision and control of hardware, software, and human resources (*brainware*).
- 5) Efficiency Efficiency describes the level of optimization of resource usage. System efficiency has a lot to do with proper division of tasks as well as an effective workflow structure.

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- 6) Service Quality is an important criterion in assessing the quality of the system. In information systems, improving services to users is often the main goal of development. Deficiencies in service quality can be shown through:
- The system generates inaccurate information,
 - The system generates inconsistent information,
 - The system produces products that have a low level of trust,
 - A system that is not easy to learn
 - Systems with complicated operation,
 - A system with a low level of ease of use,
 - Systems with limited system flexibility.

4. Violence Complaint Levels

Reporting of cases of violence can be done directly or indirectly. Direct reporting occurs if the victim or complainant comes directly to the relevant agency, namely UPTD PPA or LK3 Social Service, or contacts by phone. Indirect reporting is done by mail, *E-mail*, or *Fax*. In addition, reports from the public and other institutions are also included in the category of indirect reporting [10].

In practice, the victim went to the nearest UPTD PPA or LK3 unit. With the help of a receptionist or security, reports are recorded based on identity data (KTP). Furthermore, verification was carried out by the relevant sections to determine whether the case included gender-based violence or politically charged. The victim also received information about counseling and health services. Reports that do not match will be rejected, while reports that are declared valid are forwarded to the *Monitoring* to be processed within a maximum of 14 working days [10].

5. System Analysis and Design

The analysis and design of the system in this study aims to support the implementation of research and improve the efficiency of the workflow at the Center for Gender and Child Studies (PSGA) IAIN Datuk Laksemana Bengkalis. At the planning stage, it was found that the existing gender-based violence reporting system still uses manual procedures. Therefore, the implementation of a web-based reporting system is proposed.

1. System Analysis

System analysis is the breakdown of a complete information system into its component parts with the aim of identifying and evaluating various problems, opportunities, obstacles that occur and expected needs so that improvements can be proposed. To build a web-based system regarding complaints of gender-based violence at the Center for Gender and Child Studies (PSGA) IAIN Datuk Laksemana Bengkalis, the author first planned a workflow based on the needs of the users who will use the web suggested by the author. As for before the web was created, the author had to analyze the system that is running today. The current system is not optimal in storing or providing information, because the system currently used still uses a manual system such as for example victims of violence must be involved first to come to the protection office or the information on violence obtained is still minimal because of the lack of promotion and the lack of willingness of victims to complain about the events they experienced. If using the system that will be designed, the user no longer needs to come to the office to report, just visit the website that will be designed by the author.

2. PIECES Analysis

To assess the weaknesses of the running system, the method (*Performance, Information, Economy, Control, Efficiency, Service*) [7].

a. Performance

In the old system, officers had to actively search for victims or record case data manually, which took a long time. In the new system, users can input data independently, significantly reducing the workload of administrators.

b. Information

In the old system, case data was mostly stored in the form of paper documents without a database, making it difficult to access information.

c. Economy

Legacy systems incur high costs in terms of time, labor, and materials, especially due to the use of paper and storage space requirements. The new system reduces those costs through database-based storage.

d. Control

Older systems have a fairly high risk of data loss. Meanwhile, the system that will be designed risks of file loss can be reduced because the data has been stored in the system database.

e. Efficiency

The process of manually searching for data on an old system takes a long time. The new system allows for quick data search through databases.

f. Service (Service)

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In the current system, in providing information on trial data that will be carried out, the schedule is only pasted on the mading. This method is still not optimal because the files contain data information stored in Ms.excel media and report files on paper, so it takes precision to find it and victims who want to report the violence that happened to them must first come to the office of the Center for Gender and Child Studies IAIN Datuk Laksemana Bengkalis to report what happened to them while the system that will be built at this time knows that the user does not need to come to the office anymore because Complainants only need to visit the system that will be built, namely the Gender-Based Violence Complaint Information System.

3. Diagram Context

Context This diagram describes the relationship between the system and external entities as well as the input and output data flows.

Diagram Context Images

The image above shows the system flow, where users input data through forms, administrators manage and consolidate that data, and generate reported case reports.

4. Flowchat Plans

Flowcharts visually depict the stages of the process and their logical sequence. The process starts from the system is run until it is completed. If there is an error in filling in the user data or *login* data, the system automatically returns to the home page and prompts the user to repeat the fill.

a. E-Mail

Flowchar User Image

From the image above, it is explained that the flowchat user who opens the application to complete the complaint stage by creating a user account, if the account creation is successful, the user continues the login process by entering the user's name and password, then the user inputs Name, Gender, Email, TTL, Address, Phone No., Complaint Description, Upload ID Card, Upload Photo/Video of violence, the next process is for the user to submit a complaint, if successful, then the complaint is completed, if it fails, the user re-inputs the process and is sent back, the process is complete, the user receives a reply from the Admin via email the report received and awaits the next process.

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b. Admin

Flowchar Admin Image

In the image above, it explains the flowchat login that the admin responds to the user that the status of the report is received for follow-up, the next process is that the admin makes a recap of complaints and groups of complaints, the admin makes a report to the leadership.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Desain Application.

The design of the application for complaints of gender-based violence cases consists of Admin data and Case Reporter Data.

1. Admin

Admin login or admin data functions to capture the data of the reporter who has entered the application, so that the admin responds to the worker that the data has been recap and will be given information and then action will be taken. After the admin makes a case data record, the admin will provide the data to the related parties to take the action to be taken. For admins, it can be seen in the following image:

1) Admin Login Page

Admin Login Page Image

From the image above is the Admin login page to input Username and Password, Then Click the Login Button.

2) Admin Dashboard Page

On this page, Admins can view the Complaint statistics information.

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Admin Dashboard Page Images

3) Complaint Menu Page

On this page, the admin can see the list of complaint data

The screenshot shows the 'Laporan Pengaduan' page with a table of complaint data. A green 'Export Excel' button is visible above the table. The table has columns for '#', 'Nama Lengkap', 'Jumlah Pengaduan', and 'Aksi'. The data rows are as follows:

#	Nama Lengkap	Jumlah Pengaduan	Aksi
1	Muhammad Zidnal Falah	1 Berkas Pengaduan	Lihat Dokumen
2	Karianda	0 Berkas Pengaduan	Lihat Dokumen
3	Suryanti	0 Berkas Pengaduan	Lihat Dokumen

Complaint Menu Page Images

From the image above, the admin can see a list of complaints about gender-based violence. To Export to Microsoft Excel all documents submission Admin can press the button shown on **number 1**, to view the details of each document Admin can press button **number 2**.

4) Complaint Details Page

On this page, Admins can view the detailed information of each user who filed a complaint.

The screenshot shows the 'Detail Pengaduan' page for a specific complaint. The title is 'Detail Dokumen Pengajuan MUHAMMAD ZIDNAL FALAH'. Below is a table with the following data:

No.	Nama	Dokumen	Pengajuan	Aksi
1	Muhammad Zidnal Falah	Lihat Dokumen	31 Juli 2023	[Trash Icon]

Red boxes labeled '1' and '2' are present on the image. Box '1' highlights the 'Lihat Dokumen' button, and box '2' highlights the trash icon.

Complaint Detail Page Image

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From figure 4.6 above, the Admin can see the submission document, namely by pressing the button shown on **number 1**, the Admin can also delete the submission document by pressing the button shown on **number 2**.

5) Complaint Report Document Page

On this page, the admin can view the submission documents from the user

Complaint Report Document Page Images

In the image above, the Admin can print documents by pressing the button shown on **number 1**, to download the user's ID card, the Admin can press the button shown on **number 2**.

6) Email Compose Menu Page

On this page, admins can send emails to users.

Write Email Menu Page Images

7) Email Recap Page

On this page, admins can see a recap of email deliveries that have been made

Email Recap Page Images

From the image above, the admin can see the details of the reporter's email, by pressing the button shown on **Number 1**.

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8) Email Details Page

On this page, the Admin can see the Email Details that have been sent to the user

Email Detail Page Images

2. User

User data, i.e. the user is a reporter who reports cases of violence that occur against himself or the surrounding environment, the design of user data can be seen in the following image:

1) Register Page

Create an account to file a complaint by clicking the Submit button

Image Register Page E-Mail (user)

In the image above, Users can register by completing the biodata listed in the application field, namely entering Full Name, Username and Password to create an account, after which Click the Create Account Button.

2) User Login Page

User Login Page Image

In the image above, the User can log in by entering the Username and Password that has been created at the time of registration, then Click the Login Button.

3) User Dashboard Page

On this page, users can view information to file a complaint.

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User Dashboard Page Image

In the image of the Dashboard page above, the User can see information to file a complaint about cases of violence that occur in or around him, namely by the User (User) who can fill in a complaint by pressing the complaint input button.

4) Complaint Input Page

This page Users can view the form to file a complaint

Complaint Input Page Image

In the image of the User Input Halaman above, the User can view the form and fill in the data of the violence case that occurred to file a complaint, After the Form is filled out completely, then click the Submit button. There will be a successfully sent notification and a notification via registered email.

Email Notification Page Image

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In the image above, it shows a notification from the system email that is sent to the User's email as a notification that the application data has been received.

5) Complaint Document Information Page

On this page, users can view the information on complaints that have been filed.

Complaint Document Information Page Images

In the image above, *the user* can file a complaint more than 1 time, by pressing the button shown on **number 1**, to see the input results can press the button shown on **number 2**, to delete the complaint document can press the button shown on **number 3**, for information that has been received by the admin, you can see it by clicking the button shown on **number 4**.

6) Complaint Document Page

On this page, users can see the information on complaints that have been filed

Complaint Document Page Images

In the image above, the User can see the information of the complaint that has been filed. To print the complaint document, you can press the button indicated **Number 1**.

B. Implementation

System implementation is the stage after the system development process is completed, which is the stage when the system is officially implemented into the actual operational environment. This stage includes all programs built on the system design process, so that the system can be run and used by users normally [11].

When the system enters the implementation stage, users can start using the web-based system. Users can access the website through a search engine, then enter the URL address: <https://pkbg.org/> on the browser's address bar to enter the system view.

1. Admin Login Form Page

This page is dedicated to administrators. To be able to access the system, administrators must enter a valid username and password. If the authentication information does not match, access to the system will be denied. A more detailed explanation of the page appearance can be seen in the following image.

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Admin Login Image

After successfully logging into the system, administrators can view information on complaints that are being handled. In addition, administrators can also manage and recap case data, as well as submit reports to authorized agencies, to support the follow-up and case monitoring process.

2. User Home Page

This page is intended for general users and is used to display the content as well as the main functions of the website. The structure and appearance of the page in more detail can be seen in the following image.

Web Home Page Images

Web home page view (Gender-Based Violence Complaint Website: (<https://pkbg.org/>))

In the image above, the user as a pioneer can click the **Complaint Now Button** or **the Complaint Menu**, then the worker can register, after completing the registration the reporter can log in again in the **Login menu**. After logging in by entering **the user's name** and **passport** that has been made by the pioneer, then he can convey or report the case that occurred to him or the surrounding environment with an accurate report accompanied by pictures or videos of the incident and upload the reporter's ID card, so that the case report can be acted upon as a recap of the case report data by the admin and given to the relevant parties to follow up on the case based on the report.

After the complaint of a case of violence from the complainant, the admin can see the complaint case from the complainant and the admin recap the case, to be informed to the authorized parties to follow up on the case. The admin provides a reply in the form of information Actions taken by a team of experts authorized to handle cases of victims of violence through Email and Wa.

V. CONCLUSIONS

With the existence of this gender-based violence case complaint information system application, after the application design, implementation and analysis, it can be concluded that the User (user) as a pioneer can access the web page (<https://pkbg.org/>) and can click the **Complaint Now Button** or **the Complaint Menu**, the reporter can register so that the user can log in with the user's username and password. After **logging in**, the pioneer can submit or report cases that occur to himself or the surrounding environment with an accurate report accompanied by pictures or videos of the incident and upload the reporter's ID card, so that the case report can be acted upon as a case report recap data by the admin and the case report by the relevant government can follow up on the case based on the report. Furthermore, *the Admin* provides replies and follow-up information through email and the reporter's response, in the form of information on actions that will be taken by the relevant government and a team of experts authorized to handle cases of victims of violence based on the case recap through Email and Wa.

Based on the application that has been made, it can make it easier for the public and the relevant government to report and postpone victims of gender-based violence. The people of Bengkalis Regency can easily report acts of violence that occur to themselves and the surrounding environment quickly through [the https://pkbg.org/](https://pkbg.org/) website. Through [this website https://pkbg.org/](https://pkbg.org/) makes it easier to make reports of gender-based violence that occurs in Bengkalis Regency. Violence reporting data is well stored in the database.

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The relevant government and expert teams can follow up on cases of gender-based violence based on a recap of the case report by *the admin*.

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